

STRUCTURE, COMPOSITION AND FUNCTIONS OF THE DEFENSE DOCTRINE OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation. This article examines the Defense Doctrine of the New Republic of Uzbekistan through the prism of its structural structure, functional tasks and legal and political essence. The article systematically analyzes the four major components of the doctrine (political, strategic, economic aspects and general provisions) and the scientific and terminological description of the fundamental legal and military concepts (separate period, military conflict, hybrid threats, etc.). The role of the document in creating an atmosphere of trust and openness in international relations is revealed.

Keywords. Defense doctrine, military security, principle of openness, military-political aspect, military-strategic aspect, military-economic aspect, armed conflict, military aggression, security dilemma, separate period.

In today's global security crisis and the intensification of asymmetric hybrid threats, every sovereign state must have a legal foundation that clearly defines its military-political direction. The Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan is the main strategic document for organizing the country's defense potential, modernizing the Armed Forces, and preventing external threats. This article analyzes the institutional structure of the updated Defense Doctrine, its domestic and foreign policy functions, and the legal nature of the basic categories in the military sphere.

The Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan defines the principles and approaches to ensuring the national security of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the military sphere.

The Republic of Uzbekistan confirms the defensive nature of the Doctrine. The Republic of Uzbekistan does not consider any state to be its enemy and builds relations with all countries on the basis of the priority of the country's national interests and taking into account the generally recognized principles and norms of international law, mutual benefit, equality and non-interference in the internal affairs of other states, the resolution of all disputes by peaceful means and negotiations, and the recognition of the inviolability and immutability of established interstate borders.

Is based on the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the National Security Concept and other legislative acts, relies on the principles and norms of international law, the Charter of the United Nations, as well as international treaties to which the Republic of Uzbekistan is a party;

Proceeds from the national interests of the country, the military-political situation in the world and in the region, the level of threats to national security in the military sphere, the nature of modern military conflicts;

Takes into account the main provisions of the Concept of Foreign Policy and other documents on planning the country's defense;

reveals the directions and methods of organizing the activities of the state, society and citizens in the prevention of military conflicts, protection of vital national interests;

determines the priorities of the state's future defense policy, the main principles and directions of training, building and using the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The implementation of the Doctrine is carried out within the framework of a single state policy to ensure the national security of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Section I. General provisions

Section II. Military-political aspect

Section III. Military-strategic aspect

Section IV. Military-economic aspect

40 ARTICLES (in editing)

The updated Doctrine, first of all, provided openness and increased the level of awareness of the views, rules and principles set forth in the Doctrine by society, employees of state bodies and personnel of the Armed Forces.

In the field of security and defense, difficulties in conducting foreign policy with foreign partners have been eliminated, mutual trust has been ensured, and attempts by foreign special units to obtain information about a closed document have been eliminated.

The doctrine uses the following basic concepts:

a separate period - the period starting from the moment of the decision on mobilization (introduction of martial law), including the entire period during which military operations are carried out;

national defense - a system of political, economic, military, socio-legal, informational, organizational and other measures ensuring the sovereignty, territorial integrity, peaceful life and security of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the peaceful life and security of its population;

threats to national security in the military sphere - factors characterizing the real possibility of the use of military force against the Republic of Uzbekistan;

illegal armed formations - armed associations, detachments, groups formed in violation of national and international legislation, pursuing terrorist, extremist, criminal or other goals;

threatening period - a period of varying duration, as a rule, preceding the outbreak of a military conflict and characterized by an extremely tense military-political situation;

emergency - a situation that has arisen in a certain territory as a result of an accident, disaster, dangerous natural phenomenon, natural or other disaster that may lead to or has led to the loss of human life, damage to their health or the environment, serious material losses, and disruption of people's living conditions;

armed conflict - a limited-scale armed conflict (action, quarrel) aimed at resolving economic, political, national, ethnic, religious and other conflicts between states (international armed conflict) or between opposing parties within the territory of one state (internal armed conflict), in which a state of war is not declared;

military conflict - a form of resolving conflicts between states or within a state with the use of military force, which includes all types of armed struggle, including wars and armed conflicts;

military aggression - the use of military force against the sovereignty, territorial integrity and independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan;

military security - the state of protection of national interests from threats to state security in the military sphere.

In conclusion, the structure and conceptual content of the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan indicate that the military-political strategy of our country is fully consistent with the norms of international law. This document, consisting of 4 sections and 40 articles, not only regulates the activities of subjects in the military sphere, but also demonstrates to the global community the principles of peace-loving and multi-vector foreign policy of Uzbekistan.

The classification of terms such as “military conflict”, “armed conflict” and “illegal armed formations” in the doctrine based on clear legal criteria allows national security forces to correctly prioritize threats and develop adequate defense strategies against them in the conditions of modern hybrid, asymmetric and networked wars.

Most importantly, the updated Doctrine's reliance on the principles of openness and transparency legally strengthens Uzbekistan's position as a leading state in Central Asia, responsible for security and geostrategic stability, predictable and ready for equal military-diplomatic cooperation with all sovereign entities.

List of used literature:

1. National Security Concept of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – Tashkent. – 1997., - P.13.
2. Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan. – T.: Uzbekistan, 2018., – P.17.